

**DEVELOPING STUDENTS' LANGUAGE IDENTITY THROUGH TEACHING
COGITATING AND COMMUNICATING IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

S. Khusnetdinov¹

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to consider the process of forming the student's linguistic personality by teaching the thinking skills of information interpretation and communication within the framework of the technology of critical thinking development. This goal is conditioned by the need to develop the student's ability to think not only in the native language, but also in a foreign language for further successful implementation of educational activities. The scientific novelty of the study lies in the consideration of the possibility of using techniques related to the technology of critical thinking development for the development of thinking and communication skills in a foreign language contributing to the formation and improvement of language personality of students of higher educational institutions. The result of the study is a set of tasks developed within the framework of critical thinking technology, which allows teaching students thinking skills of systematisation of information and communication in a foreign language, thereby contributing to the formation of student's linguistic personality.

Key words: professional education, foreign language, language personality

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The relevance of this study is conditioned by the increasing attention of specialists to the topic of "language personality" and the need to consider this concept not only in theoretical but also in practical terms. It should be noted that this direction of research is not innovative, but there is still a need for its practical consideration in order to consider this topic in terms of specific stages of development and formation of language personality of students of higher educational institutions studying a foreign language.

In order to achieve the above objectives, the following research tasks were formulated: the first one is to consider the components of linguistic personality from the point of view of the possibility of emphasising on them, in the process of teaching a foreign language. The second task, which is also the practical significance of the study, is to create a set of tasks aimed at developing thinking and communication in a foreign language to achieve the goal of forming a competent linguistic personality of higher education students. To solve these problems we used such research methods as: deduction method, method of generalisation of positive advanced teaching experience and systematic approach of studying theoretical sources, which allowed us to identify the key components of linguistic personality and plan the work aimed at the development of these components, the level of development of which is directly reflected in the formation of linguistic personality in university students The

¹ *Khusnetdinov Salavat Samatovich, teacher at SamSIFL*

theoretical basis of the study was provided by the works of I.A. Zimnya [3], E.V. Ivantsova [5] and O.D. Kropotkina, T.P. Frolova [6], considering "language personality" in terminological and practical terms, which laid the foundation for the reasoning about language personality as a necessary competence for a student learning a foreign language.

As it is known, higher education includes not only a set of systematised knowledge and skills that allow solving theoretical and practical problems in a certain profile, but also the formation of the student's personality. At the same time, the formation of the student's personality seems to be especially relevant when teaching foreign languages. This statement is justified by the fact that the teacher needs not only to develop the learner's personality, but also to help in the formation of the language personality of the future specialist. Language personality, in its turn, is a person's ability to create and perceive texts that differ in the degree of structural and linguistic complexity, accuracy and depth of reflection of reality, certain target orientation. At the same time, it includes social, psychological, ethical and other components inherent in "personality", refracted through the discourse of a language.

The formation of personality is impossible without communication, receptive and productive processes that ensure the exchange of thoughts between people. Contrasting "linguistic personality" with "personality", it should be noted that one of the main distinguishing features is a person's thinking. As practice shows, the results of a person's reasoning in a foreign language may differ from the conclusions drawn in the native language. On this basis, there is a need for thoughtful development of thinking abilities and formation of information competence of students in a foreign language [1,170], [5,25].

Information competence as a pedagogical category fulfils cognitive, communicative, adaptive, normative and interactive functions. These functions are closely related to each other and actually represent a single process aimed at identifying and solving problems in different areas of knowledge.

Information competence is inextricably linked to thinking. One of the main actions of thinking is "systematisation" - a thinking operation, as a result of which the totality of knowledge is arranged in a logical chain in accordance with the set goal" [7,175].

In addition, the ability to systematize is part of a variety of personal competences, e.g.:

1. The ability to analyse a situation, reformulate it into a problem;
2. Identify knowledge deficits;
3. Evaluate the appropriateness of filling knowledge gaps;
4. accurately define goals of an activity; identify means and lists of options for solving problems;
5. Select means to solve a problem;
6. Perform actions to solve problems and achieve goals [4,60].

Analysing the above, it can be noted that the process of systematisation, which provides a large number of intellectual actions, includes analysis, synthesis and interpretation. In line with these considerations, the authors of the work consider it possible to use the technology of critical thinking in the process of developing the ability to systematise information for the formation of linguistic personality of students of higher educational institutions studying a foreign language (by the example of English). The use of critical thinking technology in the process of teaching the skills of systematisation allows to develop a thoughtful attitude to information, intellectual abilities of students,

the ability to consider different points of view on phenomena - allows students not only to carefully study the perceived information, but also on the basis of the skills formed by this technology, to construct their own knowledge, to get positive emotions from the learning process, to realise themselves and their linguistic personality [8,12]. Moreover, this technology solves the issue of communicative culture development through the implementation of a three-part learning structure, in the process of which students understand the value of their own work and feel unity with their classmates, which contributes to the development of a sense of camaraderie among students. Thus, during communication there is a constant process of self-evaluation, an understanding of the importance of correct argumentation of one's own opinion is formed, and motivation for learning in general increases [2,12].

Thus, the authors believe it is possible to offer a set of text-based tasks aimed at improving students' communicative and thinking skills, which contributes to the development of the student's linguistic personality.

Task A. To teach students to analyse information:

1. Pre-textual stage of work. Actualisation of students' life and speech experience, example of a communicative task: "Please remember and try to guess what periods of developing technology can be divided the human's history into?";

2. Textual stage of work. Work on the text during reading, an example of a communicative task: "Please read the extracts and arrange them into the correct chronological order and point out the most important facts in each extract";

3. Post-textual stage of work. Conducting reading comprehension control, example of communicative task: "Fill in the columns of the table basing on the content of the text";

4. Assigning the content of the communicative activity of reading. Production of a mini-monologue based on the result of the activity obtained at the post-text stage of work, example of communicative task: "Make up a mini-monologue on each column of the table".

Thus, in the process of performing the presented tasks, aimed at working on the text in order to develop the ability to analyse information, students identify key information in the text, distribute the parts of the text in a certain sequence and characterise the parts of a certain object, which corresponds to the actions that belong to the sphere of analytical abilities.

Task B. To teach students to synthesise and transform information:

The next stage of work is to form the skill of synthesising information presented in a text, i.e. to coordinate the characteristics of some parts of one text and combine the parts into a whole. To solve this task, it seems possible to use already available analytical material for logical and step-by-step achievement of the goal.

5. Work carried out on material that has already been analysed. An example of a communicative task: "Make up a time-line based on the analysed information and write down the most outstanding features of the ages. Try to determine what is common and what is unique in each age using the time-line". In the process of solving this communicative task, students learn to identify and summarise common and special features when comparing two or more subjects, which helps to develop their ability to synthesise information;

6. Organising a discussion in a foreign language. An example of a communicative task: "Using the time-line, tell us that your stage of technology development seems to you the most significant in the human history".

Considering the proposed set of tasks aimed at developing the ability to systematise information in group work on the text, it is important to emphasise once again that the skill of systematisation consists of two interrelated actions - analysis and synthesis, on the basis of which the tasks of the formative stage were formulated, as this division of tasks seems to be particularly effective and relevant for achieving the goal.

Summarising the above-mentioned, we can emphasise that the formation of the student's linguistic personality is impossible without focusing on the development of thinking and communication of the learner in a foreign language. The organisation of work on the development of the ability to systematise information and group work, in this case, allows to comprehensively and effectively contribute to the formation and development of the student's linguistic personality, necessary for his/her further professional activity.

As a result of the study, a set of tasks within the framework of critical thinking technology is presented, containing productive tasks aimed both at the formation of thinking skills of students and the ability to systematise in particular, and the development of oral and written productive skills that ensure communication in a foreign language. Taking into account the dual purpose of the proposed tasks, it seems possible to assert that the fulfilment of these tasks allows to effectively form and develop the language personality of higher education students.

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